

Report D3.11

“Populated repository for sustenance and
FAIRness assurance of harmonised ontologies”

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“Populated repository for sustenance and FAIRness assurance of harmonised ontologies”

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Lead author	Arkopaul Sarkar (ENIT), Nasreddine Boucheme (ENIT)
Contributors	Emna Lakani (ENIT)
Peer reviewers	Hedi Karray (ENIT)
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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
RDF	Resource Description Framework
OWL	Web Ontology Language
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

Keywords

Ontology; Ontology catalogue, Web interface

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

Task 3.2 of OntoCommons project focusses on identifying and reviewing (i.e. classification and evaluation taking into account different criteria including FAIR principals) the current picture in the area, which includes existing semantic data documentations (including ontologies, standards, databases, etc.). Originally, this task targeted to make existing domain ontologies findable and accessible through an online Registry, for which a web repository called “OntoCommons ontology catalogue” was set up. In an amendment to the contract, OntoCommons also included a FAIR-enabled more robust and permanent FAIR repository as a deliverable under Task 3.2. This report describes the features and architecture of IndustryPortal which is deployed by ENIT as a global repository for industrial ontologies.

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1. Introduction

To pursue OntoCommons goals of identifying and reviewing semantic resources related to domains such as industry, manufacturing, construction, and materials, etc, T3.2 “Domain-specific semantic Landscape Analysis” conducted a domain ontology state-of-the-art. Additionally, the OntoCommons ontology catalogue (D3.3) is set up as a website available at <https://data.ontocommons.linkeddata.es/index> containing the metadata of many of these domain ontologies.

However, OntoCommons ontology catalogue encodes machine readable data for these semantic assets only at the meta-level. At the same time, OntoCommons ecosystem endorsed another ontology repository, IndustryPortal, for persistent storage of the ontology source files along with many other facilities, e.g., version management, FAIR metadata, evaluation metrics, and content browsing services, including vocabulary search, annotator, recommender and mapping, based on NCBO BioPortal technology. In this report, the IndustryPortal with all its available features is presented first in Section 2, and then the technical architecture of the IndustryPortal is presented in Section 3.

2. IndustryPortal: features

IndustryPortal (<http://industryportal.enit.fr>), is a portal of industrial semantic resources, collecting semantic resources (primarily ontologies) from various sources, storing them, and providing search, exploration, and utilization services for these resources. Thus, it serves as a shared space for various users and applications to publish, discover, and use semantic artifacts. Besides collecting and offering ontologies, IndustryPortal offers various features related to these resources, including ontology search, ontology recommender, ontology mappings, ontology fairness assessment, and visualization of ontologies.

From a user end, the interaction with the IndustryPortal happens in an interface, that offers entries to interact with all the features that the portal offers. These interactions will result in the initiation of processes to deal with the users' needs. From a general point of view, the architecture of the portal contains 4 major parts, shown in Figure 1, like mentioned the interface will be responsible for offering a way for users to interact with semantic artifacts, and communicate the requests with the portal's API which will eventually, depending on the need, will communicate with annotator, in order to annotate texts to related ontologies concepts, as well as communicating with Ncbo Cron to order the execution of various operations on the resources available on the portal.

Figure 1: IndustryPortal Generale Architecture

Being an ontology repository, Industryportal is used as one of the tools across the ontology life cycle, in Figure 2, in the reuse phase, the portal facilitates the reusability of ontologies, by offering easy access to them and their metadata. On the other hand, once an ontology is finished being implemented and documented, the portal comes in handy as a way to publish the newly developed ontology, as well as keep track of its versioning and explore the differences between each version of the ontology.

Figure 2: Use of IndustryPortal in different ontology engineering phases

The various features that the portal offers, enable its users a better exploit and comprehend the ontologies available there, In Figure 3, we put more light on how IndustryPortal features are mapped to the different steps of Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology, which is an ontology engineering methodology. Most importantly, IndustryPortal provides several ways to find an existing ontology for reuse, e.g., using an upper-level ontology for some domain application, or to model application data, e.g., search ontology by name, category, topic, group, and other metadata, by class or certain term, or by using a Recommender service. Fig. 4 shows an illustration of the IndustryPortal features for an ontology. While using more than one ontology for implementation, users can also ensure mapping among the ontologies by using or editing the mappings stored in IndustryPortal (computed by LOOM matcher by default but new mapping may be added manually or via API). Most importantly, newly developed ontologies can be submitted to IndustryPortal or an existing ontology may be automatically updated with a new version.

Figure 3: Used tools in the ontology lifecycle

The portal uses MOD version 2.0 (Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication Ontology), which allows annotation of an ontology by a myriad of metadata to increase its FAIRness and evaluate it against O'FAIRe (Ontology FAIRness evaluator). O'FAIRe is a specialized methodology crafted for the assessment of ontology FAIRness. that supports the required metadata model. It was originally developed to provide scoring and guidance to improve FAIRness of an ontology. Last, a robust ontology mapping management utility is being developed to enable users to store complex (description logic compliant) mappings among classes along with detailed metadata and exchange them in Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM) format 2. Later, we will curate and improve the rudimentary mappings between the archived ontologies with rich metadata.

In order to facilitate Ontology comprehension and offer an intuitive way to represent ontology, IndustryPortal connects to a third-party tool called SousleSens(<https://souslesens.enit.fr/vocables/>), which is a suite of tools specially designed to navigate, compare, visualize, and enrich SKOS vocabularies and OWL ontologies. This tool is being integrated into industryPortal in a way to have a ready visualization of every ontology. Figure 4, shows an example of the Souslesens tab in ontology SSN's details in IndustryPortal.

Figure 4: Representation of SSN ontology in SOusleSens tab in IndustryPortal

3. IndustryPortal: Technical Architecture

The architecture of IndustryPortal follows a service-oriented architecture, comprising independent components. Each of these components performs specific functions and offers interfaces for interconnection. They use a standardized JSON format for communication between components or through dependency management.

Figure 5 illustrates the UML component and deployment diagram of the existing IndustryPortal architecture, depicting the interfaces between the architecture's components and their dependencies. We describe these components as follows:

Ontologies API:

Responsible for implementing the HTTP RESTful web service, serving JSON-LD data for various resources like ontologies, classes, and related endpoints such as search, annotator, and recommender. These resources are interconnected through links, similar to web pages.

Bioportal Web UI:

As previously mentioned, this is the frontend part of the platform, built on Ruby on Rails. It provides web interfaces that utilize and manipulate the REST API. It includes features like an ontology browser, annotator, recommender, ontology tree visualization, graph visualization, deployable widgets for other websites, an administrative interface, and more. The 'ontologies API Ruby client' component facilitates the connection with the API.

Ncbo Annotator:

Also built on Ruby on Rails, it is used by the REST API for text annotation.

Ncbo Cron:

Comprises Ruby and shell scripts that run periodically to manage various operational tasks, such as ontology analysis or deletion, generation of annotator dictionaries and caches, calculation of metrics, and processing of mappings.

Figure 5: An overview of the SAREF4INMA ontology in the summary page from the IndustryPortal

Ontologies Linked Data:

Within IndustryPortal, Linked Data ontologies contain models like ontologies, classes, instances, etc., which are used by the REST API. This component ensures their serialization, converting complex data stored in the triple store into native objects that can be easily manipulated and presented in various formats such as JSON, XML, or other content types. Additionally, Ontologies Linked Data provides deserialization to convert parsed data back into complex types, which are then stored in the triple store. This serialization operation is carried out using graph-oriented objects (Graph-oriented objects, GOO).

OwlAPI Wrapper:

A command-line tool that integrates OWLAPI for the analysis and interpretation of RDFS, OWL, and OBO ontologies.

Fairness:

The FAIRness evaluator (fairness assessment tool) is a Java-based web service that automatically performs tests to assess how a semantic resource conforms to a set of FAIR quality evaluation questions, resulting in a FAIR score for that resource. The service responsible for calculating the FAIR score, called O'faire, uses a set of principles called FAIR principles based on MOD 1.4. Each of these principles is divided into sub-conditions that the ontology must satisfy. In case these conditions are met, the ontology is assigned a corresponding score."

Figure 6: IndustryPortal Technical Architecture

On the other side, as mentioned earlier, Industryportal integrates a third-party tool for ontology visual representation and edition called Souslesens, since this tool could operate independently of Industryportal, and could also query the API to get ontology source files on its own, the connection between the portal and souslesens, happens in the user interface part, without the need to explicitly define a connection between the backend and the tool (knowing that tool can and already does that), the figure 7 shows how this tool works with IndustryPortal, and what are the steps followed to achieve the integrated visualization for each ontology hosted in the portal(refer to this link for more technical details about the tool).

Figure 7: Souslesens Integration in IndustryPortal

4. Conclusions and Perspectives

This document presented a brief overview of Industryportal, which is hosted and maintained at ENIT and served to the industrial community to respond to their needs regarding ontology collecting and offering.

IndustryPortal serves as a crucial platform for managing and utilizing industrial semantic resources, primarily ontologies. Its role in the ontology life cycle is pivotal, supporting ontology reuse, publication, and versioning. The portal's various features enhance users' ability to exploit and comprehend ontologies, aligning with the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology. The portal now hosts more than 100 industrial ontologies which were uploaded by the user community of the portal, please refer to Annexe A to see more details about these ontologies.

Looking ahead, several perspectives for enhancing IndustryPortal's capabilities are on the horizon. These include the extraction of metadata from ontology sources, improved version and change management, upgraded Meta-FAIR integration, ontology quality metric calculations, SSSOM-based contextual ontology network generation, federating with other portals, integration with ontology engineering toolchains, and enhanced security through email verification. On the other hand, since the OntoCommons project is coming to an end, it will be mandatory to have a clear plan that addresses the long-term sustainability and maintenance of the portal.

Finally, as IndustryPortal continues to evolve and expand its offerings, it remains committed to facilitating the seamless management and utilization of ontological resources within the industrial domain.

5. References

Emna Amdouni, Arkopaul Sarkar, Clement Jonquet, Mohamed Hedi Karray. IndustryPortal: a Common Repository for FAIR Ontologies in Industry 4.0. 22nd International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC) - Demo & Poster, Nov 2023, Athens, Greece. (hal-04207343)

6. Annex A: Ontologies in IndustryPortal and their Fairness

The following table provides an overview of the ontologies hosted on IndustryPortal along with key fairness statistics related to each ontology. These statistics include information such as ontology acronym, fair score, and score for each of F.A.I.R elements.

Table 1: List of ontologies and their FAIR stats in IndustryPortal

Ontologies	Fair score	Findable	Accessible	Interoperable	Reusable
REC	45	54	79	27	25
OMG	45	53	79	27	25
BIMERRM	39	43	79	26	14
COINS	47	58	79	33	23
VERONTO	43	46	79	33	20
DBO	39	43	79	26	14
VVO	40	43	79	31	14
REACT	40	43	79	31	14
ITSMO	40	43	79	31	14
IFCOWL	39	43	79	26	13
IOF-AV	48	53	81	43	22
DCMATERIALS	39	43	79	26	14
BIMERRW	39	43	79	26	13
SSN	53	71	81	44	23
BIMERRKPI	39	43	79	26	14
EMMO	47	53	79	44	21
IFC-PROPS	39	43	79	26	13
BPO	39	43	79	26	14
MBSE ONTOLOGY	44	49	79	41	14
SIMP	48	49	81	41	27
MEP	39	43	79	26	14

QUDT	39	43	79	26	13
BIMERRIO	39	43	79	26	14
I40KG	41	45	79	31	14
EEPSA	40	43	79	31	14
IMAMO	48	51	81	37	30
SAREF	40	45	79	27	14
BCAO	39	43	79	26	13
SAREF4SYST	40	43	79	31	14
UNSPSC	40	43	79	31	13
ELI	39	43	79	26	14
ORGO	40	43	79	31	13
MDO	50	57	81	44	25
EXTRUONT	55	56	81	57	32
GOPPRE ONTOLOGY	42	41	79	34	18
DCC	39	43	79	26	13
SAREF4BLDG	40	43	79	31	14
MASON	46	47	81	37	23
OBPA	39	43	79	26	14
FUNSTEP	48	47	81	38	32
BIMERRAO	39	43	79	26	14
OPM	39	43	79	26	14
DCPROCESSES	39	43	79	26	13
FOG	39	43	79	26	14
DCENTITIES	39	43	79	26	13
DCENERGY	39	43	79	26	13
SAREF4INMA	51	61	81	42	28
BIMERRRP	39	43	79	26	14
CONT-ONT	41	45	79	31	14
DCAGENTS	39	43	79	26	13
SWO	39	43	79	27	15

MBSE	62	67	86	55	46
SEAS	39	43	79	26	14
BIMERRMP	39	43	79	26	14
RESPOND	40	43	79	31	14
BOT	39	41	79	26	14
SOSA	39	43	79	26	13
IOF-MAINTENANCE	47	45	79	44	27
STY	34	43	79	5	14
SAREF4ENER	40	43	79	31	14
Z-BRE4K	40	43	79	31	14
DCINFORMATION	39	43	79	26	13
FALCON	41	45	79	32	14
DCAT	41	51	79	26	14
DCOCCUPANCY	39	43	79	26	13
IDDO	39	43	79	26	14
VAR	41	45	79	31	14
PRONTO	46	50	79	38	22
MTO	39	41	79	26	14
OELE	27	36	77	0	1
SCOR	48	51	79	41	28
GI2MO	45	46	79	32	27
MANUSERVICE	40	41	79	31	14
BONSAI	39	45	79	26	14
CHAMEO	40	43	79	27	18
ROMAIN	46	51	79	44	18
IAO	47	51	79	44	20
BIMERRSD	39	43	79	26	14
DCVARIABLES	39	43	79	26	13
TRIBONT	48	64	79	33	23
SAREF4ENVI	40	43	79	31	14

SAREF4CITY	40	43	79	31	14
MSDL	43	45	79	37	18
EMMO-MECH-TEST	40	43	79	26	18
DEMO	39	43	79	26	14
PSS	39	45	79	26	14
BIMERROP	39	43	79	26	14
BAO	39	43	79	26	14
IOF-PPS	27	36	77	0	1
SRO	39	41	79	26	14
RSWO	56	66	81	49	34
OPENADR	39	43	79	26	14
SCOPRO	39	45	79	26	14
BIMERRB	39	43	79	26	14
BEO	39	43	79	26	14
DCLIFECYCLE	39	43	79	26	14
IOF-CORE	49	54	79	44	25
BFO	39	43	79	26	13
LKIF-CORE	39	43	79	26	14
RGOM	52	65	81	44	25
GRACE	39	43	79	26	14
SOHO	48	53	79	44	23
BRICK	39	43	79	26	14